

The 100 varieties screened could be divided into five response groups (see table). Long-jiang-ao, Radiation 8-1, B-8, and Pioneer 1 were tolerant of butachlor; Long-jiang-dao, B-8, Wu-jie gu, and Er-jiu-nan 1 were tolerant of thiobencarb. IR30, IR54, and Fu-yu 1 were susceptible to both herbicides. □

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Grain quality and nutritional value

Induced variation in aromatic rice cultivars

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Traditional aromatic varieties Karnal Local and Bindli were irradiated with 30 kR gamma rays to obtain semidwarf, nonlodging mutants that retain parental cooking quality characteristics. Only morphological mutants were selected and grown to the M₅ generation.

Important agronomic traits were recorded on five randomly selected plants per mutant. Bulk milled rice samples were used for grain quality analysis.

All short-statured mutants selected from Karnal Local tend to lodge and are near or inferior to the parent in yield per plant (see table). Mutants KLM-14 and KLM-24 possess longer and finer grains with desirable alkali spreading value and amylose content. Except for Karnal Local Mutant-8 (nonaromatic), all mutants have strong aroma.

All mutants selected from Bindli are strongly aromatic. Mutants below 100

cm height have thick, sturdy stems and relatively upright, dark green leaves. Bindli Mutants (BM) 34, 65, and 68 have desirable alkali spreading value and amylose content. BM64 is taller than its parent.

Early-maturing aromatic strains, whether land races or developed through recombination breeding/mutation, that flower and mature at higher temperature and relatively high humidity do not develop aroma or develop only mild aroma. BM21 and BM24, despite having very short durations, maintained strong aroma and parental level of amylose content and alkali spreading value when they flowered and matured in Sep in North India. □

Range and mean for induced variations.

Character	Karnal Local	24 mutants of Karnal Local			Bindli	23 mutants of Bindli		
		Range	Mean ^a	SD		Range	Mean ^a	SD
Plant height (cm)	135.60	76.00-134.40	104.53	15.35	146.40	86.80-172.10	101.04	21.65
Tillers (no./plant)	15.00	10.00- 22.00	15.00	3.18	13.00	6.00- 17.00	12.12	2.60
Yield (g/plant)	29.30	4.50- 29.30	20.17	5.85	20.84	5.62- 37.14	21.19	7.85
Test grain weight ^b (g)	23.00	17.00- 25.80	21.10	2.31	18.00	10.50- 20.00	18.07	2.24
Filled grains (no./panicle)	85.00	20.00-103.00	65.72	20.33	80.00	57.00- 140.00	94.58	20.36
Duration (d)	150.00	132.00-164.00	152.64	10.88	161.00	110.00- 166.00	156.60	15.00
Length (L) of milled rice (mm)	7.55	6.95- 8.88	7.62	0.47	4.77	3.22- 4.80	4.56	0.36
Breadth (B) of milled rice (mm)	1.78	1.40- 2.23	1.82	0.18	2.58	2.20- 2.68	2.52	0.12
L/B ratio	4.24	3.37- 5.80	4.22	0.64	1.85	1.74- 1.92	1.80	0.09
Alkali spreading value	3.00	3.00- 4.00	3.56	0.50	4.00	3.00- 4.00	3.78	0.41
Amylose content (%)	25.5	17.00- 29.50	24.02	4.02	27.00	23.00- 29.00	25.16	1.28

^aIncludes parent. ^bOne thousand randomly selected grains used to compute test grain weight.

Hua-03 — a high-protein indica rice

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Hua-03 is a newly released high-protein, early indica variety with wide

Table 1. Some agronomic characteristics and protein content of Hua-03. ^a Wuhan, China, 1983-88.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Protein content (% dry wt brown rice)
Hua-03	113	76.96	568.13	54.20	25.20	7.0	13.72
Guang-Lu-Ai 4	117	63.31	511.21	53.16	25.18	6.2	10.50

^aMean of 5 sites.

adaptability in Hubei, Hunan, Kiangsi, and Kwangsi Provinces (23.0-32.0° N, 107-120° E). It was derived by anther culture from IR8/Er-Jiu-Qing F₂ during 1978-88. The new variety usually ripens 3-5 d earlier than popular local variety Guang-Lu-Ai 4.

In regional large-scale plantation trials in Hubei and Kiangsi 1986-88, average yield was 7 t/ha, nearly 10% higher than that of Guang-Lu-Ai 4 (Table I). Hua-03 has better nutritional quality and palatability and higher milling rate.

An outstanding characteristic of Hua-03 is its high-protein content, especially of the eight essential amino acids (Table 2). Brown amino acid score (based on lysine) was 67% in preschool children and 89% in school children. □

Table 2. Amino acid analysis of Hua-03 brown rice.^a

Essential amino acid	Content (mg/g protein)		
	Hua-03 (mean of 5 analyses)	FAO/WHO standard	
		Preschool child	School child
Isoleucine	56	28	28
Leucine	87	66	44
Lysine	39	58	44
Methionine + cysteine	37	25	22
Tyrosine + phenylalanine	107	63	22
Threonine	32	34	28
Tryptophan	12	11	9
Valine	64	35	25

^aCompared with FAO/WHO suggested requirement patterns for preschool and school children.

elongation follows a complex pattern of inheritance. We studied the relationship between physicochemical components and grain elongation in 121 quality rices, including many aromatic types, during 1987 wet season.

The experiment used a simple lattice design with two replications. Each variety was transplanted in four rows of 17 plants each at 15- × 20-cm spacing. Normal irrigated rice cultural practices were followed. Quality characters were measured 3 mo after harvest.

Twenty varieties showed more than double grain elongation during cooking (see table). Domsiah (Iran), HR59, Basmati Maher 381, Muskhon 41, Basmati 213, Basmati type-3 (Dehradun), HBC5, and HBC45 (Haryana Basmati collection) showed excellent grain elongation, with the typical beaded appearance of cooked grains (see figure). Basmati Kamon, Basmati 370, Basmati 397, Basmati 43A, HBC30, and HBC34 also are promising as donors of linear grain elongation. □

Linear grain elongation during cooking of rice varieties in Hyderabad, India, 1987 wet season.

Variety	Raw grain length (mm)	L/B ratio	Cooked grain length (mm)	Elongation ratio
<i>With very high elongation</i>				
Domsiah	6.84	4.12	18.0	2.63
HR59	5.21	3.32	12.75	2.44
Basmati Maher 381	6.74	4.0	15.25	2.26
Muskhon 41	6.64	4.0	14.75	2.22
Basmati 213	6.76	4.17	14.92	2.21
Basmati type-3 (Dehradun)	6.61	4.15	14.5	2.19
HBC5	7.79	4.72	17.0	2.18
HBC45	7.12	4.44	15.42	2.16
<i>With high elongation</i>				
Basmati Kamon	6.89	4.26	14.83	2.15
Basmati 370	6.73	4.28	14.5	2.15
Basmati 397	6.74	4.34	14.42	2.14
Basmati 43A	6.37	4.0	13.5	2.12
HBC30	7.79	4.72	16.47	2.11
HBC34	7.08	4.53	14.91	2.10
Basmati 410	7.24	4.24	15.08	2.08
Basmati 405	6.62	4.0	13.67	2.06
Basmati 242	6.49	3.93	13.32	2.05
Pakistan basmati	6.78	4.14	13.75	2.03
HBC40	6.96	4.3	14.08	2.02
Dehradun basmati	6.99	4.29	14.08	2.01
Mean	6.82	4.20	14.76	2.16
LSD (0.05)	0.83	0.56	1.38	ns
CV (%)	5.8	6.4	4.5	8.1

Sources of cooked rice grain elongation

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Elongation of rice grains during cooking is one of the unique features of Basmati rices. Some of the key Basmati traits—slenderness, translucency, and aroma—R simply inherited and easy to transfer into other genotypes. But linear grain

Cooked grain of rice varieties showing high linear elongation. Hyderabad, India